

FIG 1

FIG 2

these continuous variation studies. For the calculation of stability constant, a method previously employed by Mukherjee and Dey^{5,6} was used. Equilibrium constant of the equation may be represented as:

$$K = \frac{C[\text{NbO}(\text{5S}\cdot\text{3N}\cdot\text{Sal})_2]}{(C_{\text{Nb}})(C_{\text{5S}\cdot\text{3N}\cdot\text{Sal}})^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

using two concentrations a, a' and b, b' of the reactants, having the value of X , the same absorbancy, we have

$$K = \frac{X}{(a-X)(b-2X)^2} = \frac{X}{(a'-X)(b'-2X)^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

On simplification, we have the equation

$$4X^2[(a+b)-(a'+b')] + X[b'^2 - b^2] + 4(a'b' - ab) + (ab^2 - a'b'^2) = 0 \quad \dots (3)$$

From the graph it was determined that

$$\begin{aligned} a &= 1.0725 \times 10^{-3} & a' &= 0.726 \times 10^{-3} \\ b &= 1.050 \times 10^{-3} & b' &= 1.1725 \times 10^{-3} \end{aligned}$$

Now solving the above equation (3), we get the value of $\log K$. The average value of $\log K$ is 6.782101 which shows that the complex is highly stable.

Effect of ions

A large number of standard solutions containing anions and cations was prepared. The effect of these ions on optical density of the system was studied. It was found that Ti^{2+} , W^{6+} , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Na^+ , Cl^- , I^- , F^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} and tartarate do not interfere. Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mo^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , VO_2^{2+} ,

Cr^{3+} interfere in the formation of the coloured complex and should be removed if this reaction is to be studied quantitatively.

Discussion

The composition of the yellow complex formed by interaction of Nb(V) and 5-sulpho-3-nitro-salicylic acid as indicated by Job's method is $[(\text{5S}\cdot\text{3N}\cdot\text{salicylic acid})_2\text{NbO}]^{3-}$. There is a close resemblance in the reaction of Nb(V) with salicylic acid, 5-sulpho-salicylic acid and 5-sulpho-3-nitro salicylic acid. It indicates that linkage occurs with carboxyl and phenolic groups^{7,8}.

References

1. A. N. MELDRUM and N. W. HIRWAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 7, 889.
2. S. KALLAMAN, "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", Ed. I. M. Kolthoff and P. J. Elvin, Interscience Publishers, N.Y., 1964, Part II, Vol. 6, p. 237.
3. E. LASSNER and R. PUSCHAL, "Chelates in Analytical Chemistry", Ed. H. A. Flashka and A. J. Barnard Jr., Marcel Dekker Inc., 1969, Vol. 2, p. 217.
4. F. FAIRBROTHER and J. B. TAYLOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4946.
5. A. K. MUKHERJEE and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314.
6. A. K. MUKHERJEE and A. K. DEY, *Analyt. Chem. Acta*, 1958, 18, 1324.
7. J. H. MULLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 1506.
8. A. K. DAS GUPTA and S. K. DHAR, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, 1953, 12B, 396.
9. G. C. SHIVAHARE and D. S. PARMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, (communicated).